

SPORT IS LIFE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648369>

Abstract: This article talks about sports and a healthy lifestyle, which are increasingly deviating from the daily needs of our lives, and gives recommendations for us.

Key words: Sports, fantastic, mental health, concentration, high speed, optimization.

Sport has long ceased to seem fantastic to us, it is literally an integral part of our life, part of our being. In ancient Greece, only Olympic athletes were engaged in sports, now anyone can go in for sports. Completely different from different types to different loads. Everyone can choose a sport to their liking and according to their physical capabilities. No special halls or places are required for sports, social status or the amount of income for sports does not matter – everyone just wants and is not lazy. Therefore, if you decide to play sports, know that you are a great person !

This means that you decided not to stand still, but to go forward in development and want to stay young and healthy for as long as possible. A little about the benefits of a solution that will change many lives for the better, how a person who goes in for sports will benefit.

Promote health, improve the physical condition of the body.

The most obvious benefit of sports is to promote health. You strengthen your immunity – scientists have proven that people who play sports are less sick. The most obvious benefit of sports is to promote health. You strengthen your immunity – scientists have proven that people who play sports are less sick.

Improving mental health

In addition to the physical condition, many have seen an improvement in mental health. Sport has a positive effect on reducing anxiety, because during exercise, the body produces serotonin, which, when released into the brain, reduces anxiety and depression. Moderate regular exercise also improves concentration. Improved blood flow has a positive effect on brain function. There is no need to talk about how important it is in times of high speed, constant stress and competition.

Sports as a means of losing weight.

Everyone at least once in their life thought about how pleasant it would be to lose weight, or at least a little extra weight. Someone wants to look good in the summer and conquer hearts, and for someone, losing weight has become a vital necessity due to various unpleasant reasons and bad health. Many people start playing sports for this reason and for good reason. After all, thanks to sports, not only extra pounds are lost, but also the necessary balance develops in the work of all body systems. You will immediately improve significantly, both physically and mentally.

These reasons are already enough to go in for sports, and if you decide on this, then you will face the issue of optimizing and organizing your sports activities. Many begin to go to the gym, where they have everything they need. By attending gyms today, first of all, we can ensure our health and family peace of mind. A healthy fan and healthy views in a healthy family.

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